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The exergetic efficiency of agricultural processes, including the regeneration of soil

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1. Introduction

Agricultural processes are fundamental for providing food, yet they are significant consumers of energy. Detailed studies have quantified energy use in open-field agriculture across the European Union (EU) at a minimum of 1435 petajoules (PJ), equivalent to approximately 3.7% of the total EU energy consumption[1]. Additionally, the greenhouse gas emissions associated with agriculture pose a significant environmental concern. Beyond emissions, extensive farming exacerbates other critical issues, such as soil degradation. In Europe, it is estimated that 60–70% of soils are in poor health, posing a serious risk to sustainable food production and the essential ecosystem services that support human well-being. The financial burden of soil degradation across the EU is substantial, exceeding €50 billion each year [2].

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach is widely employed to evaluate the environmental impacts of agriculture, including energy consumption. However, LCA methods fail to account for soil quality and fertility, leading in some cases to more favourable results for intensive agricultural systems due to their higher yields per hectare (van der Werf et al., 2020). This oversight can disadvantage agroecological practices in comparative assessments, despite the fact that intensive agriculture frequently degrades soils to prioritize short-term production. However, assessing soil comprehensively is challenging due to the intricate interplay of physical, chemical, and biological parameters [3].

In previous studies, we quantified the costs associated with restoring soil fertility lost or degraded by agricultural activities [4], [5]. Soil fertility is often perceived as a free natural resource; however, when fertility is depleted, its restoration incurs long-term loss of efficiency and, thus, economic costs that are not explicitly recognized. To address this, the concept of exergy has been proposed as a tool to estimate the regeneration cost of soil. Exergy, which measures the energy available to perform useful work in a system, was applied to estimate the energy required to restore soil fertility. This approach considered the exergy embodied in a theoretical remediation and regeneration process, encompassing nutrient replenishment, organic matter restoration, sodicity correction, and soil acidification mitigation.

This study aims to assess the efficiency of agricultural systems through a single metric. To achieve this, the exergy regeneration cost has been integrated into the ExROI (Exergy Return on Investment) index, resulting in the novel ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} metric. Validation using data from various field trials will demonstrate the utility of this metric and underscore the importance of incorporating soil regeneration into assessments of agricultural efficiency.

2. Methodology

Based on the EROI concept [6], Font de Mora et al [7] defined the ExROI index to include energy quality through exergy costs and assess biodiesel production. The ExROI (Exergy Return on Investment) index is an indicator used to assess the exergy efficiency of an industrial process. It measures the amount of exergy obtained as a result of the process compared to the amount of exergy invested or applied during the process. The lower the exergy cost invested in obtaining a given resource, the higher the ExROI. Until now, the ExROI index has been applied to crops intended for biodiesel production but can be used to indicate the efficiency of crops grown for other purposes (Eq. 1).

$$ExROI = \frac{\text{Exergy obtained}}{\text{Exergy invested}} = \frac{\text{Crop exergy}}{\text{Exergy cost of the agricultural process}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

The exergy obtained is considered equal to its High Heating Value (HHV). By using the HHV of the harvested biomass, it is possible to estimate how exergy is being extracted from the soil system and can be used for other purposes, such as energy production or food. The exergy invested in the process is calculated knowing all the exergy involved in the mechanical processes (tillage, sowing, harvesting, etc.), the irrigation activities, and the production and distribution of all fertilizers and inputs used.

In addition to this index, the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index will be calculated (Eq. 2). This 'net' rate not only reflects the efficiency of the system in crop production but also incorporates the effect of the agricultural process on the soil through the effort required to restore the initial soil conditions after the agricultural process.

$$ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} = \frac{\text{Exergy obtained}}{\text{Exergy invested}} = \frac{\text{Crop exergy} - \text{Exergy regeneration cost}}{\text{Exergy cost of the agricultural process}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

This approach is crucial because it recognises that simple crop production is insufficient to assess an agricultural system's sustainability. It is essential to consider the costs associated with regenerating the soil to maintain its quality and working capacity in the long term. The exergy regeneration cost was proposed as the exergy embodied in a theoretical remediation and regeneration process that could potentially restore the impacts suffered by fertile soils addressing nutrient deficiency, organic matter depletion, sodicity, as well as soil acidification [4].

3. Results

In this section, the exergy regeneration cost methodology is validated using real data obtained from field experiments. The primary objective is to evaluate the impact of the cultivation process by comparing two distinct fertilization treatments, taking the initial condition of the soil prior to cultivation as the baseline.

Field experiments were conducted over two growing seasons with two crop types (wheat and triticale) at the same location in Gea de Albarracín, Spain. Two fertilization scenarios were tested for both crops: Treatment 1 involved basal fertilization with NPK (0-30-0) at a rate of 95 kg/ha and topdressing with conventional urea at 150 kg/ha, while Treatment 2 employed basal fertilization with NPK (0-15-0) at 187.5 kg/ha and topdressing with coated urea at 150 kg/ha. The primary differences between these treatments are the phosphorus content of the NPK fertilizer used in basal fertilization and the application of coated urea in topdressing. The NPK treatments varied in phosphorus concentration and application rate, aiming to determine whether a higher dosage or a lower but more concentrated dosage is more effective. In the case of coated urea, the fertilizer facilitates a slower and more controlled release of nitrogen into the soil. In both scenarios, wheat was planted during a subsequent growing season under the same conditions except for basal fertilization, where NPK 8-15-15 at 200kg/ha is used.

	Yield (t/ha)	Crop exergy (toe/ha)	Exergy cost of the agricultural process (toe/ha)	ExROI	Exergetic cost of regeneration (toe/ha)	ExROI _{REGENERATIVE}
TRITICALE PFC	3,75	1,56	0,22	7,06	0,64	4,16
TRITICALE PFI	6,62	2,75	0,22	12,39	0,002	12,38
WHEAT PFC	8,27	3,36	0,22	15,20	0,00	15,20
WHEAT PFI	6,47	2,62	0,22	11,80	0,00	11,80
WHEAT-TRITICALE PFC	7,79	3,40	0,27	12,59	2,90	1,85
WHEAT-TRITICALE PFI	8,18	3,24	0,27	12,00	1,65	5,89
WHEAT-WHEAT PFC	8,34	3,38	0,27	12,52	4,46	-4,00
WHEAT-WHEAT PFI	7,96	3,80	0,27	14,07	3,80	0,00

Tab. 1. Summary of parameters quantified from results obtained in the 8 agronomic trials

As demonstrated in Table 1, the yields obtained exhibit only minor variations in most cases, with some yields significantly falling below the average. The costs associated with the agricultural process are quite comparable, showing no discernible differences between the innovative and conventional treatments. However, notable differences arose in the second season, when the dosage of base dressing was increased, thereby impacting overall costs. Fluctuations in yield have a direct effect on the ExROI indicator, which is the primary metric of interest. In field trials, yield variations can be attributed to a multitude of factors, including weather conditions, pests, and diseases; consequently, the reproducibility of conclusions derived from a single data point for each case study is limited.

Wheat cultivated under conventional treatment (CBP) registers an ExROI index of 15.20, a notably high value that indicates significant efficiency in terms of exergy. This value signifies that for every unit of energy invested in the agricultural process, a return of 15.20 units of usable energy is generated through the crop. This outcome is comparable to the highest values recorded for fossil fuels, such as oil and gas, which have an average global EROI of approximately 20. The impressive efficiency of wheat can be attributed to its substantially high yield (3.36 toe/ha) in relation to the relatively low costs of the agricultural process (0.221 toe/ha).

In contrast, triticale demonstrates the lowest ExROI index under the same treatment (PFC), recording a value of 7.06. Despite the agricultural process costs being comparable to those of wheat, the exergy yielded from the triticale crop is significantly lower (1.56 toe/ha), which leads to a diminished overall efficiency of the agricultural system for this particular crop. In the second season, however, the differences between crops and treatments are less pronounced, as wheat yields were similar across the various

treatments. While the PFI treatment exhibited advantages in exergy efficiency for wheat-wheat rotations, its effects were less evident in the wheat-triticale rotation, suggesting that treatment efficiency may differ based on the type of crop.

Fig. 1. Comparison of the index ExROI and ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} obtained in the different field trials.

When the exergetic cost of regeneration is factored into the index (ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}), significant variability in results is observed (see Table 1 and Fig 1). During the first season, as there are no regeneration costs associated with wheat, the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index aligns with the ExROI index except in the trial with triticale treated with PFC, where the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index indicates a notable decrease. This reduction suggests a higher inefficiency in the process and, consequently, a diminished level of sustainability.

In the second season, however, the results exhibit more pronounced differences compared to the first. Specifically, the combination of wheat after wheat, which was previously regarded as highly efficient under the PFI treatment, now appears among the least efficient when the exergetic costs of regeneration are taken into account. This shift occurs because the energy needed to restore the soil conditions post-crop exceeds the exergy gained from the harvest, resulting in a negative balance that raises concerns about the long-term sustainability of the process.

Furthermore, when examining the impacts associated with production and incorporating the costs of regeneration to revert to the initial state, it becomes evident that soils once deemed efficient—such as wheat following triticale and wheat after wheat—demonstrate reduced yields. Notably, wheat after wheat emerges as the least efficient scenario, as the effort required for cultivation and soil regeneration is equal to or even exceeds the output capacity achieved, in both the PFI and PFC treatments, indicating that this process is not efficient.

These results demonstrate that it is essential to consider not only agricultural production but also soil regeneration in order to ensure the long-term efficiency of agricultural processes, thus guaranteeing soil resource conservation and sustainability.

4. Conclusions

Crop efficiency can be evaluated using the ExROI index; however, like many assessments in agriculture, neglecting soil fertility and quality losses as fundamental parameters may lead to misleading long-term conclusions. By incorporating the exergetic cost of soil regeneration alongside the energy yielded from the crop and the exergy cost associated with the agricultural process, the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index emerges as an effective tool for gauging the overall efficiency of agricultural practices. This index not only evaluates the useful energy produced by crops but also considers the resources required for soil regeneration, thereby offering a more accurate and comprehensive measure of sustainability and efficiency within the agricultural system.

Field trial results demonstrate that the efficiency outcomes differ significantly when soil regeneration is included in the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index compared to the ExROI index. This underscores the necessity of integrating soil exergy regeneration costs into the evaluation of agricultural process efficiency. Such a holistic approach fosters more informed and sustainable agricultural

management, striking a balance between productivity and the conservation and regeneration of soil resources, thus ensuring the long-term viability of farming practices. The proposed $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ index offers a more thorough assessment of the efficiency and sustainability of farming systems, allowing for an understanding that encompasses not only immediate productivity but also the efforts required to mitigate environmental impacts and restore soil quality post-harvest.

5. References

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6. Acknowledgment

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